

A Discourse Analysis of Trump's Speech on Iran's Nuclear Deal Based on Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar

Mohammad Reza Oroji¹, Houman Bijani^{2*}, Sahar Taremi³,
Zeinab Khalafi⁴ & Saeid Moharrami Gheydari⁵

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1. PhD, Department of English, Zanjan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Zanjan, Iran.
 2. PhD, Department of English, Zanjan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Zanjan, Iran. (*Corresponding Author)
 3. M.A, Department of English, Zanjan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Zanjan, Iran.
 4. PhD Candidate, Department of English, Zanjan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Zanjan, Iran.
 5. Department of English, Zanjan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Zanjan, Iran.

Abstract

This study made an attempt to analyze one of the Ex- US president's most debatable speech regarding Iran's nuclear deal called 'the JCPOA' on the basis of Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar. This study made an effort to explore the US president's speech and functionally explore what linguistic features he had used to convey his message and impress the audience. This paper intended to analyze the speech from functional perspective and discover how metafunctions were dealt with and what kinds of processes Trump had employed. This paper also intended to find out points of departures president Trump had selected as the theme of his utterances. Trump made an endeavor to convince the world that the deal was not a good one. By using very simple sentences and the frequent use of the first pronoun 'we', he tried to decrease his distance with the audience so that they would confide in his words. His use of modality was intended to convince his audience to accept his words. He also used modal verb of 'will' to express his threat and promises. By selecting the expressions of 'Iran or the regime', 'we', 'the deal', and 'the revolutionary guard' as his most frequent themes, he highlights their prominence as they would play a great role not only in his speech but also in the Persian Gulf area. As an example of discourse analysis, this study may help readers to learn how linguistic factors help develop the textuality of the text, how they serve the political purposes of politicians, and how they enable the speakers to persuade or dissuade the audience to instill their ideologies into the mind of them.

Keywords: *Discourse Analysis, Iran, Nuclear Deal, Systemic Functional Linguistics, Transitivity.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The joint comprehensive plan of action (JCPOA) is a contract signed between Iran and the six powers of US, Russia, China, England, France and Germany, also called (5+1). This contract was intended to limit Iran's nuclear programs and monitor and control Iran's pursuit in its nuclear developments on the one hand and lift the international sanctions on its atomic programs on the other hand.

This agreement had been highly praised by international community since everybody was assured that the world was going to be safer and all the so-called threats from the Iranian government were removed. The new US administration had no sooner come into power than it said they were no longer going to accept or stand it. President Trump, as he promised during his presidency campaign, thinks the deal is not appropriately designed and thus must be

annulled or amended. On the other hand, Iran claims that it has abided by all the regulations and has been faithful to all the items mentioned in the contract. Iran further rejects any shortcomings on its side and has promised to leave the agreement as soon as the other side alters, amends, or leaves it. Iranians say that the deal is no longer negotiable.

Trump delivered a lecture in White House on Iran's fidelity or infidelity to JCPOA, and American policies towards Iran. As opposed to his previous remarks regarding designating the Islamic Revolutionary Guard Corps (IRGC) as a terrorist organization, Trump merely stated that they were going to impose tougher sanctions on it. Having claimed that Iran has fueled war in Yemen and Syria, Trump added that Iran's interference in the area has caused violence and malicious civil wars in Iraq. He further continued that Iran has backed up Assad's regime and supplied arms for its army, the weapons which are used against Syrian kids. He went on to say that Iran's actions like this should not be neglected. He claimed that Iran had not fulfilled its commitment to JCPOA and said that he asked his administration and congress to get into the deal again so that Iran cannot intimidate the world with its nuclear weapons. He furthered that his administration would do anything to prevent Iran from developing ballistic missile.

Obviously, Trump passed the buck to the Congress to decide about the United States preservation or annulment of JCPOA within 60 days. He could do it by himself without giving this responsibility to the Congress; however, he was afraid it might be regarded as unilateral withdrawal from an international concord. He went on saying that they would take any measure to prevent Iran from accessing nuclear weapons and would impose more and tougher sanctions on Iran to prevent the regime from mass production of arms.

The aim of this article was to explore whether Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar could successfully analyze texts and how the three factors of experiential, interpersonal, and textual metafunctions could uncover the true intentions behind Trump's words. In other words, we mean to show how linguistic factors can reveal non-linguistic thoughts and ideologies.

This study made an attempt to delve into the US president's speech and functionally explore what linguistic features he had used to convey his message and leave a planned impression on the audience. This paper intended to analyze the speech from functional perspective and excavate how metafunctions were dealt with and what kinds of processes Trump had employed. This paper also aimed at discovering points of departures president Trump had selected as the theme of his utterances.

This study intended to answer the following question:

How does Systemic Functional Grammar analyze the ideologically laden speech of the US president?

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL)

We use language to talk about our experience of the world, including the worlds in our own minds, to describe events and states and the entities involved in them. We also use language to interact with other people, to establish and maintain relations with them, to influence their behavior, to express our own viewpoints on things in the world, and to elicit or change theirs. Finally, in using language, we organize our messages in ways which indicate how they fit in with the other messages around them and with the wider context in which we are talking or writing. And the three categories above are used as the basis for exploring how

meanings are created and understood because they allow the matching of particular types of function/meanings with particular types of wording (Thompson, 1996, 2000, p. 28).

Experiential Metafunction

It incorporates the idea of how we linguistically experience phenomena in the universe OR how linguistically we categorize experiences. It is through this function that the speaker or writer embodies in language his experience of the phenomena of the real world; and this includes his experience of the internal world of his own consciousness: his reactions, cognitions, and perceptions, and also his linguistic acts of speaking and understanding (Halliday, 1971, p. 332). Its components are The Actor (the doer of the action), Process (the verb), and the Goal (the entity affected by the process). Experiential metafunction is mainly represented by the transitivity system in grammar.

Transitivity refers to a system for describing the whole clause, rather than just the Verb and its Object in traditional grammar (Thompson, 1996, 2000, p. 78). It shows how speakers imagine their mental picture of reality in language and how they account for their experience of the world around them. Transitivity focuses on the transmission of ideas, so it has everything to do with the experiential function of language. The way in which transitivity carries out this experiential function is expressed by process. Based on SFG, each process is made up of three components: (i) the process itself; (ii) participants in the process; (iii) circumstances associated with the process (Bloor & Bloor, 1995, 2001, p. 107). According to the types of process in English, the process can be divided into material, relational, mental, behavioural, verbal and existential process. Material, relational, mental are the three main types of processes. They are the “principal” types in that they are the cornerstones of the grammar in its guise as a theory of experience, they present three distinct kinds of structural configuration, and they account for the majority of all clauses in a text. The other three processes are located at each of the boundaries. Behavioural processes share the characteristics of material and mental processes; verbal processes share those of mental and relational processes, while existential processes are between relational and material processes (Halliday, 1994, 2000, p. 138).

Material Clauses

Material clauses are clauses of doing and happening. A material clause “interprets a quantum of change in the flow of events as taking place through some input of energy” (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004, p. 179). These processes are those in which something is done. Material processes include action verbs as Process such as kill, break, do, and work, Actors (agent of the action or logical subjects), and Goals (nouns affected by the processes or the logical objects).

Material process: **Actor + process + Goal**
He broke the window

Mental Clauses

While ‘material’ clauses are concerned with our experience of the material world, ‘mental’ clauses are concerned with our experience of the world of our own consciousness. They are clauses of sensing. A mental clause “construes a quantum of change in the flow of events taking place in our own consciousness” (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004, p. 197). Mental clauses include Sensor, mental verbs as Processes, and Phenomena (the object of the process). Mental processes could be of different kinds: Perception (see, hear), Cognition (know, realize), Desideration (want, wish), and Emotion (like, love).

Mental process: Sensor Process Phenomena

She could hear his voice.

Relational Clauses: Processes of being and having.

Relational clauses serve to characterize and to identify. The English system operates with three main types of relation: ‘intensive’, ‘possessive’, and ‘circumstantial’, and each of these comes in two distinct modes of ‘being’- ‘attributive’ and ‘identifying’ (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004, p. 216).

Table 1: Relational processes of Attributive and Identifying

	Attributive	Identifying
Intensive: X is Y	Sarah is wise	Sara is the leader The leader is Sarah
Possessive: X has Y	Sarah has a piano	The book is Sarah’s Sarah’s is the book
Circumstantial: X is at Y	The book is on the table	Tomorrow is the 10 th The 10 th is tomorrow.

Attributive

The bread is stale.

Carrier Process attribute

She was an art student.

Carrier process attribute

Identifying:

My name is Edward.

Identified process identifier

Behavioural Clauses

These are processes of (typically human) physiological and psychological behavior, like breathing, coughing, smiling, dreaming, and staring. They are partly like the material and partly like the mental. The participants who are behaving are labeled **Behavior**.

Behavioral Process: behavior + process + (range)

She gave a faint sigh.

Behaviorprocess range = behaviour

Verbal Clauses

Verbal processes are those which play a role in academic discourse, making it possible to quote and report. They are also used to exchange information. Verbal processes include say, point out, suggest, claim, assert. Somebody who says something is called Sayer (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004, p. 252).

Verbal process: Sayer + Process + receiver + verbiage + target

He repeated the warning.

Sayer process verbiage

I explained to her what it meant
Sayer process receiver verbiage
The report criticizes John's procedure
Sayer process target

Existential Clauses

These represent that something exists or happens. There is an 'existent' in every existential process:

Existing process: process + existent + circumstantial adjunct

There are some cars in the street.

Process existent Circumstance Adjunct

Interpersonal Metafunction

The clause can be organized as an interactive event involving speaker, writer, and audience. For example, in asking a question, a speaker is taking on the role of seeker of information and requiring the listener to take on the role of supplier of the information demanded. The most fundamental types of speech acts are giving and demanding. Either the speaker is giving something to the listener or he is demanding something from him. An act of speaking is interacting: it is an exchange, in which giving implies receiving and demanding implies giving a response. The commodity exchanged could be either goods-&-services or information:

Table 2: Interpersonal Metafunction in a glance

Role in exchange	Commodity exchanged	
	Goods & services	information
giving	'offer' Would you like this teapot?	'statement' He's giving her the teapot
demanding	'command' Give me that teapot!	'Question' What is he giving her?

When language is used to exchange information, the clause takes on the form of a proposition (something that can be argued about), whereas when language is used to offer and command, the clause takes on the form of a **proposal**. They cannot be affirmed or denied (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004, pp. 106-111).

Zhuanglin (1988, p. 313) mentions, "The interpersonal metafunction embodies all uses of language to express social and personal relations. This includes the various ways the speaker enters a speech situation and performs a speech act." Modality and mood play a role in interpersonal metafunction. Mood is the element that realizes the selection of mood in the clause (modal element). Mood depicts what role the speaker chooses in the speech and what role he assigns to the hearer.

Mood consists of two parts: (1) Subject and (2) Finite. Finite element expresses tense, modality, and polarity. Modality construes a region of uncertainty, an assessment of the validity of what is being said. Modality expresses the speaker's judgement towards a proposition.

It includes modal verbs (will, must, can) and modal adjuncts including mood adjuncts (temporality [already, once], modality [usually, probably], and intensity [completely, almost, rarely]) and comment adjuncts [unfortunately, hopefully, actually].

The rest of the sentence is called ‘residue’, including predicator (non-finite verb), complement (the object of the sentence), and circumstantial adjuncts (Adverbs):

Table 3: A sample of interpersonal analysis

Sister Susie	's	sewing	shirts	for soldiers
SUB	F	Predicator	complement	adjunct
Mood		Residue		

Textual metafunction

It deals with the idea of how a given clause helps develop the textuality of the text. In other words, organizing the sequence of discourse and creating cohesion are accounted for textual metafunction.

In textual metafunction, ‘Theme’ and ‘Rheme’ play a great role in the textuality of a text. **Theme** is the element which serves as the point of departure of the message; it is that which locates and orients the clause within its context. The remainder of the message, the part in which the Theme is developed is called **Rheme**.

Table 4: Theme and Rheme Dichotomy

Theme	Rheme
The duke	has given my aunt that teapot
My aunt	has been given that teapot by the duke
That teapot	the duke has given to my aunt

As Khedri, Ebrahimi and Chan (2013) claim, “the theme helps readers in meaning realization driven by choices and purposes of the writers ...”. In other words, the points of departure or the starting points also called ‘thematic structures’ are of great significance, for it highlights the prominence of the Theme, the specific choice among many choices that the writer selects. In this study, topical theme (Theme of a clause ends with the first constituent that belongs to experiential metafunction) was taken into considerations.

3. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Wang (2010) in an article entitled ‘A Critical Discourse Analysis of Barack Obama’s Speeches’ studied Barack Obama’s presidential speeches mainly from the point of transitivity and modality. Wang came to the realizations that Obama’s language was easy and colloquial, showing Obama’s intention to shorten the distance between him and the audience.

In addition, he concluded that the material process, the process of doing and happening, was used most in his two speeches, illustrating the current states of affairs, achievements, and his future plans. It seems Obama intended to arouse people’s confidence in his presidency.

His use of modality helped him to convey his message much more easily and by using future tense, he intended to present his political, economic, and cultural in the following four years. By using first person pronoun ‘we’, he intentionally made an effort to shorten the distance between him and his audience.

Kavoosi (2002) in his Ph.D dissertation studied Theme and Rheme constructions in contemporary Persian and having focused on journalistic as well as academic texts, he came to this realization that 55.6 percent of clauses start with compound themes, where as simple themes accounted for 44.1 percent in the studied texts.

Having probed into the grade four and five primary school bilingual (Armenian and Persian) students' compositions, Fahimi nia (2009), on the basis of Halliday's SFG, concluded that the most prominent sequence of themes was (textual + experiential themes) and (textual + interpersonal + experiential themes). He also came to this conclusion that Persian or Armenian monolingual students tended to use compound and complex themes, whereas simple and unmarked themes were more prevalent among bilingual learners.

Amirkhanloo (2016), in her article entitled 'The stylistics study of verbs in Hafiz' sonnets: A functional approach', delved into the processes used in the sonnets and studied the Hafiz' confrontation with the inside and the outside worlds. Accordingly, he came to this realization that material processes dealt with Hafiz' outer world, while Hafiz's use of mental processes would illustrate abstract atmospheres. The behavioral processes were used to supplement the lover-beloved interactions. His verbal processes were utilized in his debates and relational processes were used for personification in his odes. Finally, existential processes were employed in negative forms to depict that present elements in his odes did not truly exist in Hafiz' real world.

In their article entitled 'Critical discourse analysis of political speeches: A case study of Obama's and Rouhani's speeches at UN', Sharifi far and Rahimi (2015) made an effort to dig into the linguistic spin in Obama's and Rouhani's political speeches at UN. On the basis transitivity system and modality, they tried to discover how two presidents' languages could incorporate both ideology and power in their political speeches. In other words, they were after finding out how their capabilities and policies were made through language and how their political speeches were conveyed to and perceived by common people.

Behin and Sadeghi (2010) in their article titled 'A Linguistic Account of the Protagonist's Development in The Grapes of Wrath', studied the language of Tom Joad, the main character of the novel to illustrate his social position and his transformation from a young farm-hand holding a carpe diem philosophy to a socially-wise reformist. They finally concluded that the character used material and mental processes more than the others, showing his real experience of prison and his fear of the life outside the prison respectively.

In his dissertation entitled 'The Analysis of Processes in the Persian Aphasic patients' Speech on the basis of Functional Approach', Bazyar (2011) excavated the processes used in Aphasic patients' speech. He concluded that the aphasic patients' use of material processes were significantly more than that of ordinary people, whereas their use of mental, relational, and behavioral processes was significantly less, showing aphasic patients had difficulty dealing with abstract concepts and had no choice but to focus on physical events and less abstract phenomena.

In another thesis entitled ' The Analysis of Aphasia on the basis of Interpersonal Metafunction, Tohidian, Rezapour, and Bazyar (2014), having analyzed the speech of normal and aphasic people with respect to tense and modality, came to this conclusion that normal people used more modal adjuncts and they used more past tense than the other tenses.

Vazir nezhad and Pahlevan nezhad (2009) analyzed a novel with the title of ‘the lights, I turned off’ and concluded that material, metal, and verbal processes had more frequency respectively. In addition, modality was very rare in the novel, suggesting his lack of ability in expressing his ideas and beliefs.

4. METHOD

Due to the importance of Iran Nuclear Deal as a world-wide issue and from press points of view, the US President’s controversial speech regarding this deal was selected as the sample for this study. As an international deal, the JCPOA has been authorized by the international community and the previous administration of the US.

However, the current president of the US has repetitively expressed his concerns about it as he calls it a bad deal and he has kept reiterating he wants to annul or modify it, while Iran has strongly objected to the president’s decision and finds the deal fair and justified. The functional analysis of this sample might help the researcher to disclose the pure internal feelings, to uncover the implicitly intended messages said or intended to be imposed on the mind of the audience; What has really been told by the speaker and has really been perceived by the listener.

Prior to the analysis of the functions used in the sample, a review of related literature was provided. Afterwards, a statistical description of Trumps’ speech including the number of words, sentences, paragraphs, and pronouns was made. Due to the significance of the processes in terms of transitivity, all the processes were enumerated and the percentage of each and every one of the processes was given.

The six processes in experiential metafunctions were dealt with respectively and some examples were given and analyzed. From interpersonal metafunction viewpoint, first, the number of tenses (past, present, and future) was calculated. This was followed by the enumeration of modal verbs and the analysis of modality of the sample. The number of pronouns especially the first person pronouns was counted and a number of examples were given and analyzed with respect to interpersonal metafunction.

Regarding the textual metafunction, attempts were made to pinpoint the themes of the clauses. Accordingly, the themes (points of departure) were found and some theme-rheme dichotomies were given and analyzed. In the end, a conclusion was provided.

5. THE DATA ANALYSIS

Trump’s speech consisted of 1980 words, 102 sentences and 47 paragraphs. It consisted of simple words and simple and short sentences to make sure his audience understand what he was talking about. Another reason for this simplicity is that he was speaking English and this is a foreign language for Iranians so he did his best to present his message via simpler sentences and he tried to talk slowly. As the audience were varieties of people from different classes and different educational levels; therefore, he wished to shorten the distance with the audience. The calculation of mean of the sentences highlights this idea quite well. The sentence mean length in Trump's speech was 22.5 word per sentence. This feature demonstrates that Trump intended to show his tendency towards convincing the Iranian and Non-Iranian people that the deal was not appropriately designed. The following table provides us with more detailed information about the speech:

Table 5: Statistics of Trumps’ Speech

Statistical Item	statistics
Words	1980
Sentences	102
Paragraphs	47
Characters	10213
Pronouns	123
First person	55%
Second person	3 %
Third Person	41 %
Min sentence length (words)	1
Max sentence length (words)	54
Mean sentence length (words)	22.5

According to Halliday the experiential metafunction is the interpretation of human experiences. Our experience of reality is taken in terms of processes (happening, doing, sensing, meaning, being, and becoming). These processes account for the transitivity system of language and transitivity system comprises of six processes (Material, Relational, Mental, Verbal, Behavioral and Existential):

Table 6: Transitivity in Trump’s Speech

Process types	Frequency	Percentage
Material	133	62.7
Mental	15	7
Relational	28	13.3
Verbal	22	10.3
Behavioural	2	1
Existential	12	5.7

As it is crystal clear, material processes (the process of doing and happening) reached the highest peak at 133, followed by relational and verbal processes with the records of 28 and 22 respectively. The least favorable process was behavioral ones with the figure of 2. Below, examples of the six different processes are given:

Material process

A fanatical regime	Seized	power	In 1979
Actor	Mat. Rel.	Goal	Circum. Adjunct

Iranian proxies	provided	training	To operatives
Actor	Mat. process	scope	recipient

Mental Process

We	have seen	the longer we ignore a threat, the worse that threat becomes	in North Korea
Senser	Mental process	phenomenon	Circum. Adjunct

Many people	believe	that Iran is dealing with North Korea
Senser	Mental process	phenomenon

Behavioral Process

sovereign nations	respect	each other and their own citizens
Behaver	Behavioral process	behavior

The Iranian regime	can never threaten	the world	with nuclear weapons
Behaver	Behavioral process	behavior	Circum. Adjunct

Verbal Process

I	urge	our allies	to join us in taking strong actions to curb Iran's continued dangerous and destabilizing behavior
Sayer	verbal process	receiver	verbiage
I	Have ordered	a complete strategic review of our policy toward the rogue regime in Iran	
Sayer	verbal process	verbiage	

Existential Process

There	are	many people who believe that Iran is dealing with North Korea
	Existential process	existent
There	are	many destructive activities
	Existential process	existent

Relational Process

my highest obligation	is	to ensure the safety and security of the American people
Identified Token	Rel. Process	Identifier value
this deal	is	responsible for years of terrible trade deals
Carrier	Rel. Process	attribute

Interpersonal Analysis

In Interpersonal Metafunction (clause as exchange), the function of language is social interaction. In this regard, a sentence is divided into Mood and Residue. Mood, in turn, is comprised of Subject and Finite. Finite consists of Tense, Modality, and also polarity. Residue is made up of predicator (nonfinite element), complement (the Nominal Group (NG) showing the object of the sentence), and adjuncts which are represented by prepositional phrases (PP) or adverbial group (AG). With respect to the position of Subject and Finite, mood could be declarative (SUB + F), interrogative (F + SUB) or (WH sub + F), or imperative (while both SUB and F are missing).

Tenses

Tense (primary tense) means past, present, or future at the moment of speech. It is time relative to now (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004, p. 116).

Table 7: Tense of the Sentences

Tenses	Present			Past	Future
	simple	progressive	Perfect		
NO.	79	12	38	39	22
%	41.5	6.5	20	20.5	11.5

With respect to Table 7, the most frequent tense is the present tense, including simple, progressive, and perfect. The present tense accounts for 68 % of all. By using present tense, Trump tried to point out to the present state of Iran in the world and refer to its current stance and actions. The next frequent used tense is the past tense. By using past tense, Trump deliberately reported on Iran’s (sinister) position and measures in the area, emphasizing how destructive its role was. By using future tense, Trump not only threatened that he would put more sanctions on Iran and its Revolutionary Guard, but he also made promises to inhibit Iran’s power in the area.

Modality

Modality, which refers to speakers’ degree of certainty, represents speaker’s opinion or judgement regarding a statement. Modalization is when the speaker argues about the probability of propositions and includes both probability and usability. Modalization refers to the speakers’ attitude, certainty, and judgment. It also refers to likelihood, or frequency of something happening. As mentioned above, modality also includes modal adjuncts (mood adjuncts [temporality, modality, and intensity] and comment adjuncts).

Table 8: Modal Verbs

	Low politeness	Median politeness	High politeness
Positive	Can. May, could, might, dare	Will, would, should, shall	Must, ought to, need, has/had to
Negative	Needn’t, doesn’t, didn’t have to	Won’t, wouldn’t, shouldn’t, isn’t to	Mustn’t, oughtn’t, can’t, couldn’t, may not, mightn’t,

Table 9: Modality Analysis of Trump’s Speech

	Low politeness		Median politeness		High politeness	
	NO	%	NO	%	NO	%
Positive	4	13	14	56.5	1	4.5
Negative	2	8.5	4	17.5	0	0

As can be seen, modal verbs which are used to express and convey Trump’s attitudes and judgments are as follows: Low politeness modals amount to 21.5 percent, Median politeness modals account for 74 percent of all, while high politeness modals comprise only 4.5 percent. Example are:

- *Iran **can** sprint towards a rapid nuclear weapons breakout.*
- *First, we **will** work with our allies to counter the regime's destabilizing activity and support for terrorist proxies in the region.*
- *Second, we **will** place additional sanctions on the regime to block their financing of terror.*
- *When the agreement was finalized in 2015, Congress passed the Iran Nuclear Agreement Review Act to ensure that Congress's voice **would** be heard on the deal.*

Below, some examples are interpersonally analyzed:

Finally	we	will	deny	The regime	all paths to a nuclear weapon
Mood Adjunct	SUB	Finite	predicator	complement	complement
Mood			Residue		

The regime	violently	(does)-s	suppress	its own citizens
SUB	Mood adjunct	finite	predicator	complement
Mood			Residue	

Table 10: Pronouns Used in Trump's Speech

Sub/Obj Pronouns	No.	Possessive pronouns	No.
I	12	My (mine)	4
You	4	Your (yours)	0
He/she	0	His/her (hers)	1
It	10	its	22
We	19	Our (ours)	18
They	8	Their (theirs)	6

Regarding Table10, the first person plural 'we' and 'our(s)' hit the record of 37 altogether. By using first person plural, Trump deliberately intended to shorten the distance between the speaker and the audience, and thus make the audience feel closer to the speaker and his concerns. In addition, by using this pronoun, the president intentionally made an endeavor to unify his stance with the international community including the United Nations against Iran. It seems that Trump made the same cliché prominent by distinguishing 'us', and 'them'. The next highly used pronoun is 'it/its' with the record of 32. Trump repeatedly referred to 'Iran' and 'the deal' 'It(s)' was a substitute for these two terms. This figure demonstrates the importance that Trump attached to these two terms. And the first person singular 'I' and 'my/mine' were ranked third with the record of 16. By using 'I', Trump made an effort to highlight his position as the president of the most powerful country in the world.

5.2.3 Textual Analysis

"In textual metafunction, a clause is given its character as a message. The structure which carries this line of meaning is known as thematic structure" (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2004, p. 64). As mentioned above, the theme is the element which serves as the point of departure of the message and it is that which locates and orients the clause within its context. It must be emphasized that what we have considered as theme is the same as topical theme- the first group or phrase that has some function in the experiential structure of the clause (participants, process, and circumstantial adjuncts). The theme of a clause is of great importance since it is what the speaker or writer intends to start his/her clause with. It is somehow analogous with the term 'Topic' as Lambrecht refers to. Lambrecht believes that a constituent is topicalized so that the rest of the sentence can be about it. Theme, also called psychological subject, is selected by the speaker or writer to carry the highest prominence and attention on the part of the listeners or readers.

In his speech, which was on Iran's nuclear deal, Trump mentioned 'Iran', '(the) regime', and the 'deal' 17 times, 12 times, and 9 times respectively. However, in terms of topical theme, the words 'Iran', 'the regime, and relevant Iranian 'agents' were selected as the Theme of the clauses 46 times, thus, illustrating the prominence Trump intended to give to it and highlighting the attention he wanted to attract to it. He also used the pronouns 'we' and 'I' as the topical theme with the frequency of 14 and 8 respectively. This was followed by the thematic structure of 'Revolutionary Guard' with the record of 6 and 'the deal' with the frequency of 7, showing how important these two themes were to him. Meanwhile, he intentionally started his clauses two times with 'Iranian People', as he endeavored make a clear distinction between Iranian government and its people a or as Van Leewen (1996) puts it, he made an attempt to differentiate between 'the Iranian people' as 'self' and 'Iranian regime' as 'others'. In other

words, he just intended to sympathize with Iranian people. Below, some of the most important theme-rheme dichotomies are shown:

Theme	Rheme
Iran	never acquires a nuclear weapon
Iran	is under the control of a fanatical regime
Iran	seized power in 1979

Theme	Rheme
The Revolutionary Guard	is the Iranian Supreme Leader's corrupt personal terror force and militia
It (The Revolutionary Guard)	has hijacked large portions of Iran's economy

Theme	Rheme
This deal	is known as the Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action, or JCPOA
The Iran Deal	was one of the worst and most one-sided transactions
The nuclear deal	threw Iran's dictatorship a political and economic lifeline

Theme	Rheme
We	should not take lightly its sinister vision for the future
We	will work with our allies to counter the regime's destabilizing activity and support for terrorist proxies in the region

Theme	Rheme
The citizens of Iran	have paid a heavy price for the violence and extremism of their leaders
The Iranian people	long to reclaim their country's proud history, its culture, its civilization, its cooperation with its neighbors.

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Based on Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar, Trump's speech regarding Iran's nuclear deal or JCPOA was systemically analyzed. With regards to his use of short paragraphs, and the mean sentence length of 22.5 words as well as his easy language, Trump intended to shorten his distance with the audience and make himself understood to even non-native audience. By using the first person plural 'we', he tried to show how united the international community and the United States were regarding Iran's nuclear deal and Iran's stance in the area. As far as the transitivity is concerned, material process, the process of doing, reached the highest peak at 62.7 % in comparison to the other processes. By using material processes, Trump intended to refer to the actions and deeds Iran had taken by the time. He also put more emphasis on the steps he was going to take to prevent Iran from achieving its goals in the [Persian] Gulf area. The next most used process was relational processes with the record of 13.3 %, indicating Trump's inclination to attributing some negative qualities to Iran and its nuclear agreement. The relational processes were followed by verbal processes, demonstrating Trump's announcement of his threats and promises regarding this agreement. Based on the frequency of the processes, it can be realized that Trump was trying to provoke the international community against Iran and by using the pronoun 'we', he tried to attract their confidence in his beliefs. Frequently, he used the pronoun 'I' as the president of the United States to illustrate himself as the source of power as well. His use of modality and modal verbs shows that he was trying to convey his message as simply as possible. His modal verbs were of median politeness verbs used to talk to the people of all levels and attitudes. He was trying to convince all the political parties that whatever he was announcing was right and instill a sense of 'Iranophobia' into the mind of the people throughout the world. He mostly presented his issues in present

tense to illustrate the current international situations and the roles that Iran plays for the time being. He also used simple past tense to point out Iran's destructive role in the past. He used simple future tense to mark his promises that he and his administration together with the international community as well as the United Nations would not allow Iran to arouse chaos in the area. By using simple words as well as simple tenses, the president set out to persuade the people worldwide to accept his ideas and accordingly gain their trust and confidence. This study can help readers to functionally get into the minds of the authors / speakers to get the ideologies hidden behind the linguistic features of the written/spoken texts. This study illustrates that Halliday's Systemic Functional Grammar can be a beneficial tool for excavating the texts through the three metafunctions and grasping the beliefs and intentions of the authors.

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